

Title: Movement Related Cortical Potentials in a face naming task: Influence of the tip-of-the-tongue state.

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was evaluate the movement-related cortical potentials associated with manual and speech movements during a face naming task carried out by the same participants as in a previous study, in order to: 1) determine whether the slowing down of the reaction time observed in the tip of the tongue (TOT) state was caused by motor processes; 2) compare the MRCPs among the three response categories (tip of the tongue, successful retrieval and not knowing the name); and 3) determine whether the MRCPs modulated the differences in amplitude of the late negative wave among response categories. The first component of readiness potential, the negative slope, the motor potential and the reafferent potential associated with the manual response, and two components associated with the verbal responses - the speech-related motor potential and the speech-related reafferent potential - were identified. The slowing down of reaction time observed in the TOT category may be due to a temporal interruption in the motor programming of the responses due to the TOT state. The longer latency in speech-related components in the KNOW with respect to the TOT category can be attributed to the greater cognitive demands involved in the retrieval of proper names in the former category. The brain activity associated with the preparation and execution of the responses had a differential modulatory effect on the amplitude of the LNW component, which may partially explain the differences between the categories observed in the previous study by Díaz et al. (2007).

Keywords: Movement Related Cortical Potentials, tip-of-the-tongue state, speech-related movements, naming task, sLORETA/eLORETA.

1. Introduction

Naming famous people from photographs of their faces is a complex process during which different aspects of the cognitive processing can be investigated. The process involves various stages beginning with the perception of structural characteristics of a face and ending with access to the phonological lexicon and development of a phonetic plan, which may finally result in articulation of a name. The apparently easy task of recognizing and identifying well-known faces contrasts with the frequent difficulty in retrieving the corresponding names. One of the most common failures in face-naming is the tip-of-the-tongue (TOT) phenomenon, a transitory failure in name retrieval, in which the subject is certain of knowing the name and is close to retrieving it, as it has been retrieved on other occasions (Brown and McNeill, 1966).

The use of Event Related Potentials (ERPs) to study face processing has allowed determination of some psychophysiological correlates of the stages of structural analysis (Bentin et al., 1996; Bentin and Deouell, 2000; Eimer, 2000), of recognition (Milivojevic et al., 2003; Pfützte et al., 2002; Schweinberger et al., 2002), of accessing the identity (Henson and Rugg, 2003; Henson et al., 2003), and of retrieving the name (Huddy et al., 2003; Rahman et al., 2002). However, the ERP correlates of the TOT state have been evaluated in only one previous study, in a task involving the naming of faces of famous people (Díaz et al., 2007).

In the latter study of Díaz et al. (2007), participants were shown photographs of the faces of well-known people and were required to respond by pressing one of two keys on a keyboard, depending on whether they knew or did not know the name of the person, and immediately after they had to give one of three verbal responses corresponding to the following response categories: 1) KNOW: when they knew the name and stated it correctly; 2) DON'T KNOW: they did not know the name and said "Don't know", or 3) TOT: they knew the name but could not retrieve it and said "Can't remember". The ERPs time-locked to presentation of the stimulus were analyzed in a 2 second interval. No differences among the response categories were observed in relation to the parameters of the ERPs before 550 ms (P100, N170, P2, N2, and early-P3), associated with

perceptive processing, face recognition and semantic processing. The conflict that characterizes the TOT state was evident in the longer reaction times (RTs) in this response category relative to the other two. However, there were no differences among the categories in terms of the latency of the late-P3 component of the ERP, which corresponds to the time required to evaluate and classify the stimulus into one of the three response categories.

These results, longer RT in TOT and no differences in late-P3 latency, lead to the conclusion that the TOT state does not appear to affect the time required for stimulus classification, but affects emission of the response. The slowing down of the RT in TOT may thus be due to some processes related to the preparation or execution of the responses. In the present study, analysis was made of the movement-related cortical potentials (MRCPs) time-locked to the manual response, in order to test this possibility.

The mean amplitude during the time interval in which the late-P3 component was observed (550-750 ms), was significantly smaller in the TOT category than in the KNOW category. This result was related to differences between the response categories in the effective resources dedicated to stimulus evaluation and classification (involving memory search for semantic and lexical information), and was interpreted, within the model of Valentine et al. (1996), as a consequence of the failure to access the name due to the lack of sufficient activation in the lexical route, in accordance with the transmission deficit hypothesis of Burke et al. (1991).

In addition, a Late Negative Wave (LNW) was observed with the maximum amplitude at approximately 1350-1375 ms, and with significantly larger amplitude in the DON'T KNOW category than in the TOT category. In the KNOW and DON'T KNOW response categories, this component appeared after the motor response, while in the TOT category it appeared after stimulus classification (late-P3 latency) but before the corresponding motor response. This component was considered as a correlate of a mechanism of review of stimulus categorization and/or of the selected response. In the case of KNOW and DON'T KNOW responses, the participant will emit his/her response before this review has been completed, with closure of the stimulus epoch and subsequent

release of processing resources; in contrast, in TOT responses, processing resources will continue to be assigned to the search for the name corresponding to the face. As a result, the ranking of LNW amplitudes can be attributed to the amount of processing resources released after closure of the stimulus epoch: complete closure and release of processing resources in DON'T KNOW, incomplete closure in KNOW, because a subset of processing resources are probably engaged in name retrieval and in verification of whether the name retrieved corresponds to the face presented, and non-closure in TOT, due to the blockage situation. However, as the authors (Díaz et al., 2007) indicated, it was possible that these differences were also modulated by the brain activity associated with the preparation and execution of the motor responses required in the task. The analysis of MRCP may help to corroborate this hypothesis.

MRCs have been widely used to study the cortical mechanisms that control voluntary movements of the limbs. Since Kornhuber and Deecke (1965) recorded the *Bereitschaftspotential* (*BP*) or readiness potential (*RP*), related to simple and self-paced movements, several studies have been carried out in which four MRCs have consistently been recorded: the first component of the readiness potential (1st-RP), the negative slope (NS'), the motor potential (MP) and the refferent potential (RAP) (for a complete revision, see Shibasaki and Hallet, 2006). On the other hand, the speech MRCs have been less well studied, and there is only conclusive data regarding the 1st-RP component (Brooker and Donald, 1980; Deecke et al., 1986; Grabow and Elliot, 1974; Grözinger et al., 1975, 1977; Levy, 1977; McAdam and Whitaker, 1971; Tarkka, 2001; Wholert, 1993; Wholert and Larson, 1991).

The MRCs of the limbs have been well characterized in a classical paradigm requiring self-paced movements separated by 5s or more. Nevertheless, this paradigm is limited as the nature of the movement was predetermined, which may lead to a rather automatic performance of the movements across the trials (Jahanshahi and Hallet, 2003). Therefore, it is necessary to study the MRCs under less constrained movements with more complex paradigms that enable study of the effect of cognitive processes on these components. Several studies have investigated this issue

before, showing MRCPs are differentially influenced by cognitive functions such as level of intention, preparatory state and mode of movement selection in both normal (Dirnberger et al., 2000; Freude et al., 1988; Praamstra et al., 1995) and clinical populations (Praamstra et al., 1996; Wiese et al., 2004a; Wiese et al., 2004b). In the present study, we applied a reaction time cognitive paradigm in a face naming task, which can generate three response categories requiring similar sequential movements (a manual response of the right or left index fingers followed by a verbal response) but with different cognitive demand. The use of this sequential task was motivated by the need to obtain a reliable behavioural measure of the stimulus categorization (reaction time of manual response) and the need for the researcher to make the correct classification of the responses in one of the three possible categories (verbal response). This task enables identification of the possible presence of speech-related components and determination of how the greater cognitive demands in the KNOW category (retrieval and naming of a proper name differing trial by trial) than in the DON'T KNOW and TOT categories (retrieval and verbalization of the same repetitive formula trial by trial) may affect the manual and/or verbal MRCPs.

The aim of the present study was therefore characterize and evaluate the manual and speech MRCPs in the same participants as in the study of Díaz et al. (2007), with the following specific objectives:

1. To determine whether the slowing down of the RT observed in the TOT response category took place during the preparation and/or execution of the movements;
2. To describe the MRCP components in a complex reaction time paradigm and to compare them in three different response categories, DON'T KNOW, KNOW and TOT, with the aim of determining whether the cognitive differences among them have an effect on these components.
3. To determine whether the MRCPs modulated the differences in amplitude of the LNW component among response categories.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sample

From initial sample of 20 university students who participated in the study of Díaz et al. (2007), valid MRCPs averaged waveforms were obtained from 14 participants (6 men and 8 women; age range 19-24 years). All were right-handed, with normal or corrected vision, and were healthy, with no history of neurological or psychiatric disorders and had not received any medical treatment in the 4 weeks prior to the experiment. None of the participants were familiar with the protocols used in the study. The methods used in the study were approved by the local ethics committee and all participants gave their informed consent prior to their inclusion in the study.

2.2. Electroencephalographic (EEG) recording

The participants were seated on a comfortable chair in a Faraday chamber, with attenuated levels of light and noise, and were instructed to move as little as possible during the recording. Stimuli were photographs of the faces of famous people. The photos were all software-edited for homogeneity of background and with respect to contrast and average luminance. All images were in colour, showing a frontal view of the face, with clear representation of all major features, against a neutral background. Negative facial expressions were avoided, and we tended to use images with neutral or mildly positive expressions. Each subject was shown 200 photographs (10 x 13 cm), at a distance of 1 m and for 314 ms, with a subtended visual angle of 5.7° x 8.6° of arc, on a 19" flat screen monitor with a vertical refresh rate of 120 Hz.

The EEG activity was recorded on 30 active electrodes inserted in a cap (Fp1, Fp2, F7, F3, Fz, F4, F8, FT7, FC3, FCz, FC4, FT8, T3, C3, Cz, C4, T4, TP3, CP3, CPz, CP4, TP4, P7, P3, Pz, P4, P8, O1, Oz, O2), in accordance with the International 10-20 System, with a nose reference and frontopolar ground. The signal was passed through a 0.1-50 Hz (24 dB/octave slope) analog bandpass filter, the signal was amplified to 22.5 K and the sampling rate was 500 Hz. Simultaneous to EEG recordings, ocular movements (EOG) were recorded with two electrodes located supra and infraorbitally to the right eye (VEOG) and another two located at the lateral angle of each eye (HEOG). All impedances were maintained below 10 kΩ.

After signal storage, ocular artifacts were corrected by use of the algorithm of Gratton et al. (1983); the EEG was then segmented by extraction of synchronized epochs associated with each manual motor response, with a duration of 3300 ms, 2000 ms pre-response and 1300 ms post-response, which were classified a posteriori as DON'T KNOW, KNOW and TOT, depending on the participant's response. The signal was adjusted to a baseline of 500 ms (between -2000 and -1500 ms) and segments exceeding $\pm 150 \mu\text{V}$ were automatically rejected. All of the segments accepted were individually inspected to identify those still showing artifacts. Finally, the signal was passed through a digital, 0.1 to 30 Hz (24 dB/octave slope) bandpass filter and the epochs were averaged. The moment of the manual response was considered as a marker of the averaged MRCPs. For each response category, a minimum of 20 artifact-free epochs were averaged.

2.3. Procedure

Each participant was shown 200 photographs of the faces of famous people, in 5 blocks of 40 photographs, and with an interblock interval of 90 s. During the trial, the participants maintained a steady position by looking at a cross that appeared in the centre of the screen during intervals without photographs. Before the start of the trial, the participants were presented with a practice block of 10 photographs (different from the 200 photographs that formed part of the task) to ensure that they had understood the instructions. The photographs were presented sequentially.

The participants were required to press, as quickly as possible, the M key (covered with a red sticker) of a computer keyboard, with the index finger of the right hand when they were sure that they did not know the name of the person, or the Z key (covered with a green sticker) with the index finger of the left hand when they were sure that they did know the name of the person. Immediately after, they had to say aloud: 1) the name of the famous person (KNOW category); 2) "Don't know", if they did not know the name (DON'T KNOW category), or 3) "Can't remember", if they were sure that they knew the name but could not remember it at that moment (TOT category). We did not have a reliable trigger to determine the exact point in time when the verbal response started. Nevertheless, the subjects were given instructions to state their verbal response

immediately after the manual response, and given the fact that participants were young, normal subjects the verbal response always occurred immediately after the manual response.

The TOT states were therefore caused spontaneously by the task, without any type of experimental manipulation. In the case of the KNOW response category, only the EEG epochs corresponding to correct responses were considered

2.4. Data analysis

As regards performance of the participants, the number of responses and the RTs of the manual response (pressing the key) corresponding to each of the response categories (KNOW, DON'T KNOW and TOT) were evaluated.

As regards the MRCPs, the EEG epochs corresponding to each response category (KNOW, DON'T KNOW and TOT) were averaged, and thus three MRCP averaged waveforms were obtained for each participant. The values of amplitude and latency of the manual and speech-related components were measured at the C3, Cz, C4, P3, Pz, P4, F7, Fz and F8 electrodes.

Visual inspection of the waveforms revealed 6 components (see Fig. 1): the first component of the readiness potential (1st-RP) was deviated from baseline from the time of stimulus presentation in each response category; the negative slope (NS') between 500 and 100 ms prior to the response; the motor potential (MP) was identified as the maximum negative peak between the 50 ms prior to the response and the next 100 ms; after the MP, a positive-going phase was observed, with a maximum amplitude between the 50 and 300 ms posterior to the response: the refferent potential (RAP). A negative wave of large amplitude was recorded after the RAP, with a maximum peak between the 250 and 700 ms after the manual response; we denominated this the speech-related motor potential (Sr-MP). This was followed by a positive-going phase between the 600 and 1300 ms after the manual response, which we denominated the speech-related refferent potential (Sr-RAP).

In order to study the time relationships between the stimulus-onset and response-onset time-locked ERP components and to check for possible modulation of the MRCPs on the LNW

component in the study of Díaz et al. (2007), the mixed plots of the stimulus-onset and response-onset averaged ERP waveforms from 14 subjects were carried out for each response category. Thus, for the three response categories the stimulus-onset averaged ERP waveforms were compared with the response-onset averaged ERP waveforms (Fig. 2).

As regards the parameters evaluated in the different components, for the 1st-RP the mean amplitudes in two intervals were analyzed: the interval between 1700 to 1100 ms before the manual response (from stimulus presentation in TOT category to the stimulus presentation in DON'T KNOW and KNOW categories) and the interval between 1100 to 500 ms before the manual response. For the NS', the mean amplitude in the interval between -500 and -100 ms was measured. In the other components, the latency and the amplitude at the maximum peak were measured. For both MP and Sr-MP the amplitude was measured with respect to the baseline, whereas in the reafferent potentials (RAP and Sr-RAP) the peak to peak amplitude was measured with respect to the previous component (MP to RAP and Sr-MP to Sr-RAP), as these were positive deflections whose maximum peak was below zero μV and measurement at the baseline may be confusing and uninformative.

The sLORETA/eLORETA software (Pascual-Marqui, 2002) was used to compare the distribution of current density among the three response categories in each of the MRCP components. Computations were made in a realistic head model (Fuchs et al., 2002), using the MNI152 template (Mazziotta et al., 2001), with the three-dimensional solution space restricted to cortical grey matter. The intracerebral volume is partitioned in 6239 voxels at 5 mm spatial resolution. Anatomical labels as Brodmann areas are reported with an appropriate correction from MNI to Talairach space (Brett et al., 2002). Thus, sLORETA/eLORETA images represent the electric activity at each voxel in neuroanatomic Talairach space (Talairach and Tournoux, 1988) as the squared standardized magnitude of the estimated current density. Pairwise comparisons were made between the current density values at each pair of the three response categories in each of the measured MRCP time intervals. Two intervals were compared in relation to the 1st-RP (from -1700

to -1100 ms and from -1100 to -500 ms) and one interval corresponding to the NS' (from -500 to -100 ms). For the other components and for each response category, intervals of 40 ms (± 20 ms with respect to the maximum peak for each component), measured independently for each subject, were compared.

2.5. Statistical analysis

In order to compare the RTs of the participants in the three response categories, repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied, with a within-subject factor: Response Category, with three levels (DON'T KNOW, KNOW and TOT).

In order to evaluate the amplitude and latency of the MRCs, two types of ANOVA were applied: 1) repeated measures ANOVA with three within-subject factors: Response Category (three levels: DON'T KNOW, KNOW and TOT), Hemisphere (two levels: left and right) and Region (three levels: frontal lateral [FL: F7/F8], central lateral [CL: C3/C4], parietal lateral [PL: P3/P4]); and, 2) repeated measures ANOVA with two within-subject factors: Response Category (three levels: DON'T KNOW, KNOW and TOT) and Midline (three levels: Fz, Cz and Pz). When significant effects were detected by ANOVA, Tukey tests were applied for post-hoc comparison of the means. Statistical significance was considered at $p < .05$. The Greenhouse-Geisser correction was applied to the degrees of freedom when the condition of sphericity was not fulfilled.

The sLORETA/eLORETA software was used to perform voxel-by-voxel comparisons of the MRCs current density distribution. Non-parametric statistical analyses (Holmes et al., 1996; Mulert et al., 2001) were performed by use of a log-F-ratio statistic for paired samples.

3. Results

3.1. Performance

The mean percentage of responses was 42% for the KNOW category, 39% for DON'T KNOW, and 19% for TOT. The repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category) for the RTs showed significant differences among the response categories ($F(2,26) = 16$; $p < .001$), with the mean RT for the TOT category (mean: 1714 ms; SD: 708 ms) being significantly longer than for the

KNOW (mean: 1122 ms; SD: 340 ms) and DON'T KNOW categories (mean: 1136 ms; SD: 350 ms).

3.2. Movement Related Cortical Potentials

Six components were identified in the grand averaged waveforms for the three response categories (Fig. 1). The 1st-RP was clearly appreciated in the averaged waveform from the 1100 ms prior to the manual response in DON'T KNOW and KNOW response categories, whereas in the TOT response category the negativity appeared to start at around 1700 ms before the manual response, but returned to baseline until approximately 1100 ms before the manual response, coinciding in time with the late-P3 ERP component (see Fig. 2). Therefore, two time intervals were analyzed taking into account the reaction times in each response category. In the first interval analyzed (from 1700 to 1100 ms before the manual response) the maximum mean amplitude for the TOT category was registered at the Cz electrode (mean: $-1.0 \mu\text{V}$; SD: $4.3 \mu\text{V}$), whereas for the DON'T KNOW and KNOW response categories the values were positive. Neither the repeated measures ANOVA for lateral electrodes nor for midline electrodes showed any significant effect.

In the second interval (from 1100 to 500 ms prior to the manual response) the maximum mean amplitude for the three response categories was registered at the Cz electrode ($-2.6 \mu\text{V}$). Neither the repeated measures ANOVA for lateral electrodes nor for midline electrodes showed any significant effect.

The NS' was observed between the 500 and 100 ms prior to the manual response (Fig. 1), with the mean maximum amplitude at Cz ($-4.8 \mu\text{V}$). The only significant effect revealed by the repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category, Hemisphere and Region) was for Hemisphere factor ($F(1,13) = 4.3$; $p < .05$), with the mean amplitude in the interval being significantly larger for the right hemisphere (mean: $-2.7 \mu\text{V}$) than for the left (mean: $-1.6 \mu\text{V}$). The repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category and Midline) did not reveal any significant effect.

The MP reached its maximum amplitude with respect to the baseline at the Cz electrode ($-12.5 \mu\text{V}$), with a mean latency of 19 ms post-response at this location (Fig. 1). For MP amplitude,

the repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category, Hemisphere and Region) revealed a significant effect of Region factor ($F(2,26) = 13.1$; $\epsilon = .544$; $p < .001$), with the mean amplitude being significantly larger at CL (mean: $-8.4 \mu\text{V}$) and PL (mean: $-8.7 \mu\text{V}$) than at FL (mean: $-2.39 \mu\text{V}$). No significant effects were observed for Response Category and Hemisphere factors or their interaction. The repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category and Midline) revealed a significant effect of Midline factor ($F(2,26) = 5.7$; $p < .01$), as the amplitude of this component was larger at the Cz electrode ($-12.5 \mu\text{V}$) than at the Fz ($-9.9 \mu\text{V}$) and Pz ($-9.2 \mu\text{V}$) electrodes (Cz > Fz and Pz). No significant effects were observed for Response Category or the interaction nor for MP latency in any of the ANOVAs carried out.

The RAP showed a mean latency of 120 ms at Cz and at parietal lateral electrodes (Fig. 1). The maximum amplitude was registered at Cz with a mean value of $8.5 \mu\text{V}$ measured relative to the previous peak (MP). As regards the RAP amplitude, the repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category, Hemisphere and Region) only revealed significant differences for the Region factor ($F(2,26) = 4$; $p < .05$), as the amplitude was larger at CL (mean $7.37 \mu\text{V}$) than at FL (mean $6.27 \mu\text{V}$). No significant differences were observed for the other factors studied or their interaction. The repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category and Midline) also revealed significant differences among Midline electrodes in the amplitude of the component ($F(2,26) = 9.3$; $p < .01$), so that the amplitude of RAP was significantly larger at Cz ($8.47 \mu\text{V}$) than at Fz ($7.53 \mu\text{V}$) and Pz ($6.8 \mu\text{V}$) (Cz > Fz and Pz). No significant effects of the Response Category factor or of the interaction between the two were observed. The repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category, Hemisphere and Region) showed that Response Category factor had a significant effect on the latency of this component ($F(2,26) = 4.3$; $p < .05$), which was significantly shorter in KNOW and TOT (with latencies of 102 ms and 103 ms respectively) than in DON'T KNOW (with latency of 160 ms). The repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category and Midline) also showed a significant effect of the Response Category factor on the latency of the component ($F(2,26) = 4.8$; $p < .05$), and this was

significantly shorter for the KNOW (103 ms) and TOT (102 ms) response categories than for the DON'T KNOW response category (159 ms).

(Figure 1 about here)

The Sr-MP showed a mean latency of 470 ms after the manual motor response, at parietal electrodes, where the maximum amplitude was also reached, with a mean value of $-28 \mu\text{V}$ (Fig. 1). As regards the amplitude, the repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category, Hemisphere and Region) revealed a significant effect of Region factor ($F(2,26) = 48.2; \epsilon = .529; p < .001$), with larger amplitudes at PL (mean $-29.5 \mu\text{V}$) than at CL (mean $-27.9 \mu\text{V}$) and FL (mean $-19.6 \mu\text{V}$) (PL > CL and FL). This ANOVA did not reveal any other significant effect for the amplitude of this component. The repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category and Midline) showed a significant effect of Midline factor ($F(2,26) = 17.1; p < .001$), with significantly larger amplitudes at the Pz ($-29.54 \mu\text{V}$) and Cz electrodes ($-29.12 \mu\text{V}$) than at Fz ($-26 \mu\text{V}$) (Cz and Pz > Fz). No significant differences in the amplitude were observed for the Response Category factor or the interaction. As regards latency, the repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category, Hemisphere and Region) revealed a significant effect of Response Category factor ($F(2,26) = 4.1; p < .05$), which was significantly shorter in TOT than in KNOW category, (397 ms and 526 ms respectively). No significant differences in latency or its interaction were observed for the other factors. The repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category and Midline) also revealed a significant effect of Response Category factor ($F(2,26) = 4.2; p < .05$), as the latency was significantly shorter in TOT (397 ms) than in KNOW category (526 ms). This ANOVA did not reveal any significant effects of Midline factor nor of its interaction.

Finally, the Sr-RAP showed various deflections, more evident in the TOT response category, with a maximum peak close to 300 ms after the Sr-MP peak. It reached its maximum peak-to-peak amplitude and its shortest latency at parietal electrodes ($32.8 \mu\text{V}$ and 1015 ms, respectively). As regards the peak to peak amplitude of this component, the repeated measures

ANOVA (Response Category, Hemisphere and Region) showed a significant effect of Region factor ($F(2,26) = 107.2$; $\epsilon = .575$; $p < .001$), as the amplitude was significantly larger at the PL (mean: $32.84 \mu\text{V}$) than at the CL (mean: $30.77 \mu\text{V}$) and FL regions (mean: $21.86 \mu\text{V}$), and larger at CL than at FL ($\text{PL} > \text{CL} > \text{FL}$). This ANOVA did not reveal any significant effects of the Response Category and Hemisphere factors nor their interaction. The repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category and Midline) revealed the existence of a significant effect of Midline factor as regards the amplitude of this component ($F(2,26) = 68.2$; $\epsilon = .680$; $p < .05$), with a significantly larger amplitude at the Pz electrode ($32.88 \mu\text{V}$) than at the Cz ($31.77 \mu\text{V}$) and Fz electrodes ($28.18 \mu\text{V}$) and larger at Cz than at Fz ($\text{Pz} > \text{Cz} > \text{Fz}$). No significant differences were observed in the amplitude of this component for the Response Category factor or the interaction. As regards the latency, the repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category, Hemisphere and Region) revealed a significant effect of the Response Category factor ($F(2,26) = 4.7$; $p < .05$), as the latency of this component was significantly shorter in the TOT category (887 ms) than in the KNOW category (1104 ms). No significant effect was observed for Hemisphere and Region or for the interaction between them. The repeated measures ANOVA (Response Category and Midline) revealed a significant effect of the Response Category factor on the latency of Sr-RAP ($F(2,26) = 4.8$; $p < .05$), as the latency was significantly shorter in the TOT response category (885 ms) than in the KNOW category (1104 ms). No significant effect of Midline or of the interaction was observed for the latency of the component.

As regards the possible modulation of the MRCs on the LNW component of Díaz et al. (2007), the mixed plots for each response category of the stimulus-onset and response-onset grand averaged waveforms are shown in Figure 2. As can be seen, the maximum amplitude of the LNW was posterior to the late-P3 component for the three response categories. In the KNOW and DON'T KNOW categories the peak amplitude of the LNW was posterior to the RT, whereas in TOT the maximum peak of the LNW was anterior to the RT. Taking into account that the RTs were significantly longer in TOT, the LNW in the TOT category appeared some 300 ms before the

manual movement, and therefore in MRCP waveforms will coincide temporally with the interval in the NS' appears. In the KNOW and DON'T KNOW categories, the LNW will occur posteriorly to the manual response, and will coincide temporarily in the MRCP waveforms with the interval corresponding with the Sr-MP component (see Fig. 2)

(Figure 2 about here)

3.3.sLORETA/eLORETA

In the comparisons among the three response categories (Fig. 3) significant differences in the Sr-MP interval between KNOW and DON'T KNOW and between KNOW and TOT were found. Significantly larger activation was observed in KNOW than in DON'T KNOW and in TOT categories ($p < .05$) in the lateral temporal region (Brodmann areas 20, 21, 22, 38 and 42), in the lateral prefrontal region (Brodmann areas 9, 44, 45 and 47), insula (Brodmann area 13) and precentral gyrus (Brodmann areas 6, 44 and 4), all in the right hemisphere.

(Figure 3 about here)

4. Discussion

As regards the performance, the percentage of TOT responses (19%) was consistent with previous reports (Brennen et al., 1990; Díaz et al., 2007; Yarmey, 1973). The RT was significantly longer during the TOT category than in the other two categories, as observed in the study of Díaz et al. (2007) and in previous studies (Maril et al., 2001; Maril et al., 2005). In accordance with Díaz et al. (2007), we consider that the delay in the RTs in TOT reflects the unsuccessful attempt to retrieve the name. However, these behavioural parameters do not explain at what level of processing (stimulus processing, stimulus categorization, preparation or execution of the movements) the slowing down of the RT occurred in TOT.

In the study of Díaz et al. (2007), in which the ERPs time-locked to the stimulus presentation were analyzed in the same task, the slowing down of the RT in TOT condition was not

caused by a delay in face processing, as reflected in the lack of differences in latency of the components P100, N170, P2, N2, and early-P3, nor by the time of stimulus classification, reflected in the lack of differences in latency of late-P3 component, and must therefore be caused by slowing down of the preparation and/or the execution of the responses. Clarification of the latter was the first objective of the present study.

With this aim, the MRCs time-locked to the RT in each response category were analyzed. Six MRC components were found in the averaged waveforms of the three response categories: two prior to the manual response, the first component of RP (1st-RP component) and the negative slope (NS'); one immediately after the manual response, the motor potential (MP); and three after the manual response, the manual reafferent potential (RAP), and two components probably reflecting the verbal responses required in the task, the speech-related motor potential (Sr-MP), and the speech-related reafferent potential (Sr-RAP).

As regards the 1st-RP component, in the mixed plots of the averaged ERP waveforms related to stimulus-onset and to response-onset (Fig. 2) it was observed that in the DON'T KNOW and KNOW response categories, the onset of the 1st-RP coincided with the time of stimulus presentation (1100 ms before the manual response), but in the TOT response category the 1st-RP only reached a continuous negative amplitude at about -1100 ms, at the time when the late-P3 component was observed in stimulus-onset average TOT waveform. Nevertheless, given that the properties of the stimuli were the same in the three response categories, the 1st-RP probably also began at the time of stimulus presentation in the TOT category, but returned to the baseline, as reflected by the lack of significant differences in the mean amplitude at the time interval between -1700 and -1100 ms among the response categories and in the brain areas activated.

The functional significance of the 1st-RP remains unclear but has been associated with a general state of anticipation or preparation (Gerloff, 1998), as an index of resource mobilization (McCallum, 1993) or intention to act (Libet, 1983). This component may be affected by multiple

unconscious cognitive factors and appears not to depend on the part of the body executing the movement (Rektor, 2003).

Taking into account the functional significance of the 1st-RP, the data obtained for the first interval of this component probably indicate that the general mobilization of necessary resources to pre-programme the motor action is effective in the DON'T KNOW and KNOW categories from the moment of stimulus presentation, but that in the TOT state these mechanism may be interrupted until complete categorization of the stimulus (whose ERP correlate is the late-P3 component) takes place. This temporal blockage in the adequate development of the 1st-RP in TOT category may be due to the division of resources between the fruitless search for semantic and lexical-phonological information about the famous person and the motor programming in the TOT state. The influence of attentional factors on the 1st-RP has been clearly established and several studies have demonstrated that its amplitude diminished when subjects pay less attention to movement preparation (Wiese et al., 2004b). The 600 ms slowing in RT observed in the TOT response category with respect to the other two categories may therefore be due to the temporal interruption in the motor programming of the responses caused by the TOT state, until the categorization of the stimulus is completed.

As regards the second interval of the 1st-RP (from -1100 ms to the onset of NS'), when the preparation had clearly started for the three response categories, the maximum mean amplitude was observed at the Cz electrode, with a symmetrical distribution across the scalp for the three response categories, in accordance with the typical distribution of this component (Brunia and Van Boxtel, 2000; Deecke et al., 1969). The lack of significant differences in mean amplitudes among response categories at this interval leads us to conclude that from the time of stimulus categorization in TOT, the three response categories were similar in terms of the general state of anticipation necessary to prepare the motor resources.

The Negative Slope (NS') reached maximum amplitude at central electrodes (C3, C4 and Cz), in accordance with the findings of previous studies (Deecke et al., 1976; Shibasaki et al., 1980;

Tarkka and Hallet, 1990). The mean amplitude of this component was significantly larger at the right than at the left electrodes. Such lateralization is consistent with the greater number of responses given with the left hand, associated with the KNOW and TOT (61%) categories, in comparison with the lower number of responses made with the right hand, associated with the DON'T KNOW category (39%).

The NS' has been suggested to be associated with voluntary choice and the endogenous urge to act (Rektor, 2003); its distribution depends on the part of the body executing the movement (Boschert and Deecke, 1986) and is affected by features of the movement itself, like precision, discreteness or complexity of the movements (Shibasaki and Hallet, 2006). Thus, the NS' appears to reflect preparation for the specific motor program that will be performed. No differences between categories were found in this component in the present study, probably because the properties of the movements in the three categories were similar at this level (finger movement). The interhemispheric asymmetry found in this study is consistent with the important effect of the part of the body that performs the movement on this component.

The Motor Potential (MP) for all three response categories showed larger amplitudes at the electrode contralateral to the hand that made the movement (C3 for DON'T KNOW and C4 for KNOW and TOT). These results are consistent with the typical topographical and contralateral distribution of the MP described in the relevant literature regarding manual movements (Deecke et al., 1969; Shibasaki et al., 1980; Tarkka and Hallet, 1990). The latency of MP was shorter (although not significantly) in the KNOW and TOT response categories than in the DON'T KNOW response category. In the present study the manual response for the KNOW and TOT categories was made with the left hand, while the response for the DON'T KNOW category was made with the right hand - the dominant hand in all participants. This result is consistent with the data obtained in a study of Tarkka and Hallet (1990), in which longer latency of the MP was observed for the movements executed with the dominant hand than for the movements executed with the non dominant hand.

The positive component following the MP corresponded to the RAP described by other authors, and reached its maximum amplitude at central electrodes, in accordance with the P+90 and N+160 components described by Shibasaki et al. (1980). Given that the task required a verbal response immediately after the manual response, there may be a partial overlap between the RAP and the subsequent large negative component (Sr-MP), and therefore the RAP may not be completely developed. The latency of the RAP was significantly shorter in the KNOW and TOT categories than in the DON'T KNOW category, both at lateral and midline locations. The RAP is considered a correlate of the somatosensorial information that reaches the motor cortex after movement (Bötzel et al., 1997), and therefore it may be expected that the observed delay in the latency of MP with movement of the dominant hand is consolidated in RAP, as observed in the present study.

The shorter latency in the MP and RAP potentials when the movements are executed with the non-dominant hand may be tentatively attributed to the fact that the neural network that participates in genesis of these potentials is simpler for the non dominant hemisphere, and/or that the inhibitory effects on the neural network are weaker than in the dominant hemisphere. Nevertheless, these interpretations should be taken cautiously given that the manual responses were not balanced across participants and more research is necessary to check these hypotheses.

The two large components found after manual RAP are probably the electrophysiological correlates of verbal responses execution. Although we did not have a reliable trigger of the onset of the verbal responses, we believe that these components are the speech-related motor potential and reafferent potential, as the verbal responses were executed immediately after the manual response. Nevertheless, the lack of trigger for the vocal response did not let us to determine the exact onset of the verbal response, therefore a jitter effect on the speech-related components, which may have affected the amplitude of these potentials, cannot be ruled out. Both components showed shorter latencies at Cz and the parietal region, where maximum amplitude values were also reached, whereas at the frontal electrodes, significantly smaller amplitudes and longer latencies were

recorded. These data, along with the replication among categories, rule out the possibility that these components will be affected by muscular artifacts associated with the speech movements, as in this case larger amplitudes at the periphery of the EEG electrode array (frontal lateral sites) would be expected owing to their proximity to the orofacial muscles (Tremblay et al., 2008), rather than at centroparietal electrodes of the midline - where Brooker and Donald (1980) did not find any type of contamination. Although the topographical distribution of Sr-MP is predominantly central-parietal, it was widespread, an aspect that along with its large amplitude appears to reflect the activation of several brain areas and the use of numerous processing resources. The Sr-RAP peaked close to 300 ms after the Sr-MP in accordance with the P+300 component of Shibasaki et al. (1980).

Significant differences among response categories in the latencies of the two speech-related components were observed, at both the lateral and the midline electrodes; the latencies were shorter in TOT than in KNOW and there were no differences between TOT and DON'T KNOW. Taking into account that in TOT the effective preparation of the movement began later than in the other two response categories, this difference in latency cannot be attributed to differences in available preparation time, nor to differences in the phonetic properties of the utterances because these properties are reflected in the amplitude of speech-related MRCPs (Levy, 1977; Wholert, 1993).

Therefore, we consider that these differences may be due to the effect that the different cognitive demand among the response categories has on the Sr-MP; thus, the greater cognitive demand in the KNOW category than in the other two categories may explain the observed delay in the latency of Sr-MP. In the KNOW response category, the participant has to say the name of the person, which differs for each photograph; this involves gaining access to the semantic lexicon to retrieve a specific name and surname, and also gaining access to the phonological pattern to construct the phonetic plan that will be articulated. In contrast, in the TOT category, the linguistic process is simpler, as the same phonetic pattern is retrieved ("Can't remember"), which may remain active in the working memory during the whole task. Consistently, the arrival of information at somatosensorial areas (Sr-RAP) is also delayed in KNOW with respect to TOT.

In the KNOW category the delay between classification of the stimulus and the maximum peak of Sr-MP lasted approximately 900 ms. For common names the production processes may take around 600 ms, in accordance with the meta-analysis of Indefrey and Levelt (2004). In the present study the participants had to produce proper names and the greater difficulty in retrieval of proper names than in retrieval of common names is well established in the literature (for a revision see Valentine et al., 1996), as they are pure referring expressions without describing any attributes of the corresponding entity. This greater difficulty is reflected in the longer RTs found for retrieval of proper names (Proverbio et al., 2001).

It therefore appears that the TOT category modulates the latency of the speech MRCPs, not via the conflict that the TOT state generates, but rather via the lower cognitive demand associated with repeated verbalization of the same formula.

As regards the sLORETA/eLORETA analysis, differences between KNOW category and DON'T KNOW and TOT categories were found in the time interval corresponding to the speech-related motor potential. These differences revealed greater activation in right lateral temporal and prefrontal regions, right insula and right precentral gyrus in the KNOW category than in the other two categories. In addition, no differences were observed in the activation of areas in the left hemisphere. These results are consistent with the important role of the right hemisphere in the retrieval and naming of famous people names, as can be seen in several case study reports that have shown that focal right temporal lobe damage can result in impairment of the three levels of face processing: recognition, semantic identification and naming (Ellis et al., 1989; Evans et al., 1995; Seidenberg et al., 2002; Semenza et al., 1995). In addition, the greater activation in the lateral prefrontal region may reflect maintenance mechanisms associated with the name retrieved in the working memory and access to episodic information in KNOW (Tsukiura et al., 2002; Tulving et al., 1994). Activation of the right premotor region was observed by Kemeny et al. (2006) during the articulation phase in a picture naming fMRI study. The lack of differences in areas of the left hemisphere probably reflects the fact that in the three categories the areas associated with phonetic

coding and articulation can be activated in the same way because the three categories require similar mechanisms. Therefore, the greater activation of the right hemisphere in KNOW may be essential to the success in retrieval and naming of proper names.

The final objective of this study was to determine the possible modulation by the MRCPs on the LNW component obtained in the study of Díaz et al. (2007), in which a difference among response categories in the amplitude of the LNW was observed - minimal in TOT, intermediate in KNOW and maximal in DON'T KNOW, and significantly larger in DON'T KNOW than in TOT. This finding was attributed to the amount of processing-related resources that were released at the end of the stimulus epoch (complete closure and release of resources in DON'T KNOW, complete closure and incomplete release in KNOW, and incomplete closure and maintenance of processing-related resources in the search for the name in TOT). As a result, it was concluded that the LNW may be a correlate of the mechanism of review of categorization of the stimulus and of the selected and/or emitted response.

Taking into account the mixed plots of both averaged waveforms, the maximum amplitude of the LNW was posterior to the stimulus categorization in the three response categories (late-P3 component). However, in the KNOW and DON'T KNOW response categories, it was posterior to the RT, whereas in TOT it was anterior to the RT. Therefore, the LNW took place in the TOT category at the time when NS' appears, but in the KNOW and DON'T KNOW categories, it occurred posteriorly to the manual response and coincided with the interval corresponding with the Sr-MP component (see Fig. 2). This differential overlapping of LNW with the MRCP components may imply differential modulation of the LNW amplitude by these components. Therefore, the differences in LNW amplitude among the three response categories were probably not only caused by the amount of processing-related resources that were released at the end of the stimulus epoch, but also by the larger amplitude of the Sr-MP with respect to NS'.

The present data do not contradict the functional explanation provided by Díaz et al. (2007) for the LNW, since in TOT this may reflect review of the categorization of the stimulus and the

response selected, at the moment when the preparation of manual motor program starts (NS'), and in KNOW and DON'T KNOW, review of the categorization of the stimulus and the manual response emitted, at the moment that the verbal response is going to take place.

5. Conclusions

In summary, the MRCPs recorded while participants carried out a complex face-naming task, which involved the preparation and sequential execution of two types of movements (manual and verbal), showed morphological characteristics consistent with the MRCPs reported in previous studies employing simpler tasks.

We evaluated the MRCPs in three different response categories, i.e. tip of the tongue state (TOT), successful name retrieval (KNOW) and not knowing the name (DON'T KNOW). The temporal blockage in the adequate development of the 1st-RP in the TOT state may explain the slower RT observed in this response category than in the KNOW and DON'T KNOW response categories. This blockage may be due to the division of processing resources between the fruitless search for information about the famous person and the motor programming,

The specific components associated with the verbal responses (Sr-MP and Sr-RAP) showed a longer latency in KNOW than in TOT response category, which may be due to the higher cognitive demands of the verbal response in KNOW. In addition, in the time interval corresponding to the Sr-MP component, a network of areas in the right hemisphere (related with the success in the proper retrieval and naming) showed greater activation in the KNOW than in the TOT response category, probably reflecting that the right hemisphere plays a critical role in the process of naming of famous faces.

Finally, the data showed that the gradual difference shown by the LNW amplitude (DON'T KNOW > KNOW > TOT) may not only reflect the amount of processing-related resources that were released at the end of the stimulus epoch (Díaz et al., 2007), but also the differential modulatory effect of the MRCPs on the LNW amplitude in TOT with respect to KNOW and DON'T KNOW response categories.

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Figures

Figure 1. Grand-averaged MRCP waveforms for the DON'T KNOW, KNOW and TOT response categories at midline electrodes sites (1st-RP: first component of readiness potential; NS': negative slope; MP: motor potential; RAP: refferent potential; Sr-MP: speech-related motor potential; Sr-RAP: speech-related refferent potential) and voltage maps for 1st-RP, NS', MP and Sr-MP in KNOW condition.

Figure 2. Mixed plots of the grand-averaged ERP waveforms (N=14) obtained by stimulus-onset average in Pz electrode site (dotted line) and by response-onset average in Cz electrode site (solid line) for the DON'T KNOW (top), KNOW (middle) and TOT (bottom) response categories (S: stimulus presentation; RT: reaction time; I-P3: late-P3; NS': negative slope; LNW: late negative wave; Sr-MP: speech-related motor potential).

Figure 3. Brain areas significantly more activated for speech-related motor potential in the KNOW response category than in the DON'T KNOW response category (top) and in the KNOW response category than in the TOT response category (bottom).

